

SPECIFIC CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF IRON DEFICIENCY IN PREGNANT WOMEN

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The aim of the study is to identify and evaluate the specific clinical manifestations of iron deficiency anemia (IDAPW) in pregnant women in the conditions of Andijan.

Research material and methods. Iron deficiency anemia was studied and evaluated in 1500 pregnant women in a 6-year retroepidemiological screening. Questionnaire, clinical, instrumental, hematological, biochemical and statistical methods were used.

6-year results The increase in IDA production was accompanied by age-related changes in women and the following prevalence was noted: <20 – 24 90.57% ($R < 0.05$), 25 – 29 – 91.68% ($R < 0.05$), at 30-34 - 90.17% ($R < 0.05$), at 35-39 92.41% ($R < 0.05$), at 40-44 100.0% and ≥ 45 years old. – 100.0% ($R < 0.05$).

According to 6-year prospective epidmonitoring, IDA in different age groups was confirmed by different changes in specific detection frequencies: in the ≤ 20 age group with a decrease of 10.1% ($R < 0.01$), in the 20-24 age groups - from 17.9% to 8, with a decrease to 68% ($R < 0.01$), with an increase from 16.8% to 18.8% at 25-29 ($R > 0.05$), from 9.0% to 19.4% at 30-34 with an increase up to ($R < 0.01$), at the age of 35-39 - with an increase from 6.8% to 35.6% ($R < 0.001$), at 40-44 - an increase from 5.6% to 27.8% with ($R < 0.001$), ≥ 45 years old - observed with an increase from 0.00% to 75.0% ($R < 0.001$).

It can be concluded that the age of a pregnant woman is a strong risk factor in the origin and development of IDA. The main increase is observed after the age of 20 years, and more than 8 times the occurrence of IDA in pregnant women is observed from the age of ≥ 45 years.

In the years of the study, the prevalence of IDA among pregnant women in rural and urban conditions was recorded as follows, with a significant difference: in 2015 - 0.5% and 27.7% ($R < 0.001$), in 2016 - 12.1% and 31.1% ($R < 0.001$), in 2017 - 5.8% and 19.8% ($R < 0.001$), in 2018 - 16.7% and 7.0% ($R < 0.01$), in 2019 – 34.6% and 11.7% ($R < 0.001$).

During the research years, two different trends were found in IDA in pregnancy (IDAP). First, with regard to rural conditions, IDAP is characterized by a sharp increase (from 0.5% to 30.3%) over 6 years. The second, on the contrary, is characterized by a sharp decrease in IDAP in urban conditions (from 27.7% to 2.7%) (RR=1.5; II=1.1 - 0.8; $X^2=12.6$; $R < 0.05$).

According to the analytical results, the "growth trend" of IDAP in rural conditions and the "decrease" in urban conditions are observed in 2018 and 2019.

The need to improve the ferrotherapy and ferroprophylaxis system in rural conditions is clearly visible. It is clear from this that the issue of studying and determining the reasons for such a difference in the rural and urban population in the region of investigation has become urgent.

In the II trimester of pregnancy, on the contrary, there was a 3.8% increase in the prevalence of IDA ($R > 0.05$). In 2020, IDAP was recorded with a frequency of 13.9% or a relative decrease was recorded.

The trend of "growth" in the III trimester was more than 22% in pregnant women in the last 6 years, and especially since 2019, the risk of developing IDAP has increased sharply.

In general, in all three trimesters, in the last 6 years, the epidemiological risk of IDA has increased or the frequency of distribution has been confirmed.

Results and conclusions. In the study, the frequency of detection of the main clinical symptoms of IDAPW and methods of prevention were studied and confirmed. In particular, it has been confirmed that IDAPW is characterized by 3 syndromes (anemic, circulatory hypoxic and sideropenic) and 21 symptoms. Anemia syndrome is confirmed with 8 symptoms and 62.9% prevalence. The same clinical symptoms/indications are prioritized in other types of anemia than in non-pregnant women. Circulatory - hypoxic and sideropenic syndromes are detected with significantly less frequency (37.1%). This syndrome and symptoms are noted with relatively high frequencies in the III trimester of pregnancy.

In general, the analytical results confirm that differentiated ferrotherapy and ferroprophylaxis programs in different trimesters of pregnancy, a system and algorithm based on screening-epidemiological examination materials should be implemented, or this scientific conclusion was confirmed.

